

CFD Analysis of SAH System Employing Different Rib Shapes

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Abstract: The purpose of this work is to conduct a computational analysis of a roughened solar air heater (SAH) using artificial roughness in the form of several types of ribs. A solar air heater is a kind of heat exchanger that uses sun radiation to produce heat energy. Smooth solar air heaters are considered inefficient because of the poor convective heat transfer coefficient from the absorber plate to the air. To improve the heat transfer rate, artificial roughness is used in the form of double concave ribs. The geometric variables that will be selected are relative roughness height (e/D), relative roughness pitch (P/e), and relative arc radius (r/e). These variables will be analyzed at five different values of Reynolds number (Re), and their impact on heat transfer, friction factor, and thermohydraulic performance parameter (THPP) will be examined using commercial computational fluid dynamics (CFD) software, Ansys Fluent. After examining past studies, it has been concluded that the Nusselt number grows as the Reynolds number increases, and the opposite is true for the friction factor. However, when it comes to the relative arc radius (r/e), both the Nusselt number and the friction factor decrease as r/e increases. When a/H is increased from 0.2 to 0.5, the Nusselt number rises from 65.64 to 242.72, and the friction factor rises from 0.0806 to 0.2155 for the range of Re . The Nusselt number rises from 68.88 to 274.29, and the friction factor rises from 0.0876 to 0.6290 over the range of Re considered when e/H increases from 0.4 to 0.8 with a constant value of a/H of 0.3 and β of 30%. When β is increased from 13% to 30% while keeping e/H at a constant value of 0.4 and a/H at a constant value of 0.3, the Nusselt number reduces from 207.92 to 70.26, and the friction factor decreases from 0.1707 to 0.0877 across the range of Re . For a/H , the maximum Nusselt number enhancement and friction factor increment are determined to be 5.86 and 22.15, respectively. These values correspond to a/H of 0.5, e/H of 0.4, and an open area ratio of 30% for the Reynolds number range examined across the smooth duct.

Keywords: Solar Energy, Solar Radiation, Solar Cells, Solar Air Heaters, Artificial Roughness

I. Introduction

Solar energy is radiation from the sun that can produce heat, cause chemical processes, or generate electricity. The entire amount of solar energy that reaches the Earth is far greater than the energy needs of the world today and in the future. This widely available source has the ability to meet all future energy requirements if it is properly utilised. Solar energy is anticipated to become a more appealing renewable energy source in the 21st century due to its limitless supply and its lack of pollution. This is in stark contrast to fossil fuels such as coal, petroleum, and natural gas, which are limited in availability.

Solar air heating is a solar thermal method that uses an absorbing media to catch energy from the sun, known as insolation, and then uses that energy to heat air. Solar air heating is a renewable energy technique that is used to heat or condition air for buildings or process heat applications. It is usually the most affordable option among all solar technologies, particularly for commercial and industrial applications. It also tackles the major use of building energy in heating climates, which is space heating and industrial process heating.

Solar air collectors can be divided into two categories:

- Unglazed Air Collectors or Transpired Solar Collector (used primarily to heat ambient air in commercial, industrial, agriculture and process applications)
- Glazed Solar Collectors (recirculating types that are usually used for space heating)

Fig. 1 solar energy potential

(<https://cdn.britannica.com/27/198827-050-1C027B7D/Earth-power-potential.jpg>)

Flat-plate collectors are one of the most frequent devices used to catch solar energy and transform it into thermal energy. They are utilised for solar heating applications. These collectors must have a vast surface area since the intensity of solar radiation at the surface of the Earth is very low. A collector must have a surface area of approximately 40 square meters (430 square feet) in order to collect enough energy to meet the energy needs of one person, even in sunny areas of the world's temperate zones.

The most common type of flat-plate collector is made out of a blackened metal plate that is coated with one or two sheets of glass. The sunlight that falls on the plate heats it up. The heat is subsequently transmitted to air or water, which are called carrier fluids, that flow past the rear of the plate. The heat can be used

directly, or it can be transferred to another material for storage. Solar water heaters and home heating systems often use flat-plate collectors. Insulated tanks are often used to hold the water that is heated during sunny hours. This water can then be used to retain heat for usage at night or on overcast days. This type of system can offer hot water to a residence by drawing it from the storage tank, or it can provide space heating by circulating warmed water through tubes in the ceilings and floors. Flat-plate collectors usually heat carrier fluids to temperatures between 66 and 93 °C (150 and 200 °F). Depending on the design of the collector, the efficiency of such collectors (that is, the percentage of energy that they convert into usable energy) can be anywhere from 20 to 80 percent.

Solar air heat technology can be used in a range of applications to reduce the carbon footprint that comes from using conventional heat sources, such as fossil fuels, to offer a sustainable way to produce thermal energy. Solar air heat devices can be used for applications such as space heating, extending the greenhouse season, pre-heating ventilation makeup air, and process heating. Solar thermal technologies are combined with photovoltaics (PV) in the field of "solar co-generation." This combination increases the system's efficiency by cooling the PV panels, which improves their electrical performance, while concurrently warming air for space heating.

II. Problem Statement

A glazed double pass solar collector has been built (Ankush Hedau et al. (2023)) using the configuration described by previous researchers. This was done based on the objectives that were set for the current research.

Fig. 2 Solar Air Heater Configuration used in the research

The concept shown in Figure 2 includes a glazed type solar collector that uses an absorber plate with a glass cover on top of it. Plywood has been installed on three sides of the absorber plate, which is supported by glass wool and thermocole. This is done to insulate the model and prevent any form of heat movement in and out of the solar collector.

The solar collector that will be used in the current research has been selected to be a dual-pass type solar collector. Therefore, this air heater is referred to as a Dual Pass Solar Air Heater (DPSAH). Air is forced to go through the bottom section, which then moves it to the opposite side. After that, it makes a U-turn

and goes back in the original direction. Table 1 below contains all of the boundary conditions.

Table 1 Boundary Conditions for the Research

Surface	Boundary Type	Boundary Condition	Value
Sidewalls	Walls	No-Slip Walls	Adiabatic Walls
Absorbing Plate	Walls	No-Slip Walls	Solar Irradiation of 880 W/m ²
Outlet	Outlet (Pressure)	Developed	Gauge Pressure
Inlet	Inlet (Velocity)	Developed	0.73-4.6 m/s

Fig. 3 Investigated parameters of Perforated baffles

The current research investigation is being carried out in two different ways. The first method for analysing this study is based on the following factors: relative roughness height (e/H), relative roughness pitch (P/e), relative arc radius (r/e), Reynolds number (Re), attack angle, air mass flow rate, and Reynolds number (Re). The current investigation has utilised the following parameters: relative roughness height (e/D) ranging from 0.018 to 0.037, relative roughness pitch (P/e) ranging from 6 to 14, and Reynolds number (Re) ranging from 3000 to 19000.

III. CFD Analysis of DPSAH

In order to make things easier, a number of assumptions have been established before to the analysis of the DPSAH. Here are a few of them:

- The flow is constant, three-dimensional, and turbulent.
- The air is treated as an ideal gas, and its behaviour is determined by pressure and temperature.

- The physical and thermal parameters of the absorber plate and air remain constant regardless of the operation temperature.
- The bottom plate and sides of the SAH are insulated.
- The absorber plate is exposed to uniform solar radiation of 880 W/m². As a result, the radiation losses are considered to be insignificant.

The current part explains how to do a comprehensive CFD analysis of DPSAH in ANSYS in order to evaluate its performance. The following stages outline the process of the analysis-

- **SAH Modelling-** A 3D model of the DPSAH has been created and put together using the SolidWorks software suite. The SolidWorks software is used to develop the model part design module. The previous section previously discussed the dimensions of the DPSAH.

After the object is produced in SolidWorks, it is saved in one of the following formats: .iges, .igs, .step, or .stp. This file is used to analyse DPSAH in ANSYS Fluent.

Fig. 4 Meshing performed in ANSYS Fluent

A number of studies have been carried out on temperature contours and turbulence kinetic energy. The results for the same are being shown here for your reference-

Turbulence Kinetic Energy

- **Re = 9000, a/H = 0.3**

Fig. 5 Turbulence Energy Contour for Re = 9000, a/H = 0.3

- **Re = 19000, a/H = 0.3**

Fig. 6 Turbulence Energy Contour Re = 19000, a/H = 0.3

- **β = 13%, Re = 9000**

Fig. 7 Turbulence Kinetic Energy Contour for β = 13%, Re = 9000

Velocity Contours

- **a/H = 0.3, Re = 9000**

Fig. 8 Velocity Contour at a/H = 0.3, Re = 9000

- $a/H = 0.5, Re = 9000$

Fig. 9 Velocity Contour at $a/H = 0.5, Re = 9000$

- $\beta = 13\%, Re = 9000$

Fig. 10 Velocity Contour at $\beta = 13\%, Re = 9000$

- **Static Temperature Contours**

- $a/H = 0.3, Re = 9000$

Fig. 11 Static Temperature Contour at $a/H = 0.3, Re = 9000$

- $a/H = 0.5, Re = 9000$

Fig. 12 Static Temperature Contour at $a/H = 0.5, Re = 9000$

- $\beta = 13\%, Re = 9000$

Fig. 13 Static Temperature Contour at $\beta = 13\%, Re = 9000$

IV. Data Analysis & Interpretation

- **Variation in Nusselt Number & Friction factor w.r.t. Reynolds Number**

Fig. 14 Variation in Nusselt Number & Friction factor w.r.t. Reynolds Number

Figure 14 shows the numerical validation of the smooth duct SAH, which is compared to the experimental results and empirical correlations for the Nusselt number and friction factor. The numerical simulation of the conventional SAH has been determined to be the most accurate when compared to the experimental result and the Dittus bolter equation, with an average absolute percentage error of 10.4% and 9.3%, respectively, for the Nusselt number. In the same way, the average absolute percentage error for the friction factor is 12.7% for the experimental method and 10.5% for the Blasius equation.

Fig. 15 Variation in Nusselt Number w.r.t. Reynolds Number

The experimental test rig was developed to numerically validate a DPSAH with artificial roughness at an explored parameter of e/H of 0.4, an open area ratio of 30%, and an a/H value of 0.3, with the Reynolds number changing from 3000 to 15000. Figure 15 shows the experimental validation of the Nusselt number and friction factor, along with the simulation findings for the range of parameters that were evaluated. The experimental result is found to be in the best agreement with the numerical results, with a maximum absolute percentage error of 1.86% for the Nusselt number and 5.34% for the friction factor. This error occurs as a result of numerical assumptions, experimental errors, truncation errors, uncertainty, and inaccuracies in the instrument. Additionally, the total heat losses (top, bottom, and side wall) were estimated within the range of parameters evaluated, which varied from 12.66% to 5.88% as Re increased from 3000 to 19000.

• **Variation in Nusselt Number w.r.t. a/H**

Fig. 16 Variation in Nusselt Number w.r.t. a/H

Figure 16 shows that the Nusselt number values increase from 65.46 to 240.27 as the Reynolds number values increase from 3000 to 19,000 in the selected range of a/H . This is based on the change of the Nusselt number with a/H for different values of the Reynolds number. As the Reynolds number increases, the turbulence inside the rectangular duct also increases. This is due to the increase in turbulent kinetic energy that comes from the perforation holes.

• **Friction factor variation with a/H**

The Nusselt number has been improved by increasing the pressure drop of a SAH. Figure 17 illustrates how the friction factor changes with a/H for different values of the Reynolds number. When the Reynolds number is increased from 3000 to 19000, the friction factor values decrease from 0.0816 and 0.2142 for the range of a/H that is being evaluated. The roughness geometry in the absorber plate creates secondary flow behind the perforated baffles, which are located in front of the semicircular tubes. As the Reynolds number increases, the amount of secondary flow that reattaches to the primary flow also increases, and the distance at which the secondary flow

reattaches to the primary flow decreases in both the upper and lower sections of the rectangular duct.

Fig. 17 Friction factor variation with a/H for various values of Reynolds number.

V. Conclusions

A numerical examination has been conducted to examine the heat transmission and frictional characteristics of DPSAH, which has semicircular tubes and perforated baffles as the artificial roughness. An analysis has been conducted to investigate how the values of Nusselt number (N_{ur}) and friction factor (f_r) are affected by tube amplitude ratios (a/H), baffle-height ratios (e/H), open area ratios (β), and Reynolds number (Re). The following conclusions can be derived based on the findings of the numerical simulation.

- When a/H is increased from 0.21 to 0.48 while keeping e/H at a constant value of 0.4 and β at a constant value of 30%, the Nusselt number climbs from 65.46 to 240.27, and the friction factor increases from 0.0816 to 0.2142 for the range of Re .
- The Nusselt number grows from 68.78 to 264.29, and the friction factor increases from 0.0866 to 0.6390 for the range of Re -examined, when e/H is increased from 0.4 to 0.8 for a constant value of a/H of 0.3 and β of 30%.
- When β is increased from 13% to 30% for a constant value of e/H of 0.4 and a/H of 0.3, the Nusselt number reduces from 204.92 to 69.26, and the friction factor decreases from 0.1717 to 0.0887 for the range of Re .
- For a/H , the maximum Nusselt number enhancement and friction factor increase are estimated as 5.84 and 22.51, respectively. These values correspond to a/H of 0.5, e/H of 0.4, and an open area ratio of 30% for the Reynolds number range examined over the smooth duct.

VI. References

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